

Risk Assessment of Cadmium for the adolescent population in Cyprus

Abstract

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary cadmium (Cd) intake of the adolescent population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of $2.5 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ body weight (b.w.) per week and to determine the major food groups that contribute to the dietary Cd exposure in Cyprus⁽¹⁾.

Also, the current study compares the values with those values published in EFSA's relevant scientific report⁽²⁾.

Food consumption data were obtained from the Child- health Database for adolescents in Cyprus, 303 participants, which is part of the EFSA Comprehensive Database.

Cadmium occurrence data in food items (n=6705) were produced within the Official Control performed by the State General Laboratory (SGL) for the years 2003-2013 and extracted/collected from the Laboratory Management Information System (LIMS) of SGL.

The mean and 95th percentile dietary intake values were 2.03 and $4.3 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ b.w. per week, respectively. Twenty four percent of the adolescent population has a dietary Cd intake above the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) established by EFSA in 2009⁽³⁾.

Grain products, fish products & other seafood and composite food contribute to more than 50% to the Cd intake.

Materials and Methods

Food consumption data at individual level and mean occurrence data were combined and matched at level 2 of EFSA FoodEx version 1 system for categorisation and description of food⁽⁴⁾ to perform the exposure and risk assessment study. Specifically, food consumption data were obtained from the Child- health Database for adolescents in Cyprus, which includes 303 participants. Cadmium occurrence data in food, 6705 items, were extracted from LIMS at SGL for the years 2003-2013, and are shown in Table 1. Mean and 95th percentile of lower (LB), middle (MB) and upper (UB) bound cadmium occurrence were calculated for each food category by setting results below the LOD to zero, half the LOD or the LOD, respectively.

The IMPRORISK model is an empirical distribution model and it is based on the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. It was developed for SGL by IMPROVAST (www.improvast.com) and it was used in this study to calculate the Cd dietary exposure, at individual level.

Table 1: Lower bound (LB), middle bound (MB) & upper bound (UB) mean and 95th percentile (P95) cadmium concentrations in food & drinking water in Cyprus (2003-2013), for food categories at FoodEx level 1, which were used for the exposure assessment. LC% = left-censored proportion.

Food category ¹	No of Samples	Occurrence			
		mean µg/g			
		LC %	LB	MB	UB
Grains and grain-based products	30	6,7	0,019	0,019	0,019
Vegetables and vegetable products	95	46,3	0,022	0,022	0,023
Starchy roots and tubers	21	38,1	0,019	0,020	0,020
Legumes, nuts and oilseeds*	-	-	0,028	0,031	0,034
Fruit and fruit products	40	95,0	0,000	0,002	0,004
Meat and edible offal	294	58,8	0,011	0,012	0,013
Fish and other seafood	549	46,4	0,104	0,105	0,106
Milk and dairy products	237	81,9	0,000	0,001	0,002
Eggs and egg products*	-	-	0,002	0,004	0,007
Sugar and confectionary	26	100,0	0,000	0,001	0,002
Animal and vegetable fats and oils*	-	-	0,000	0,002	0,005
Fruit and vegetable juices*	-	-	0,002	0,003	0,003
Non-alcoholic beverages*	-	-	0,002	0,002	0,002
Alcoholic beverages*	-	-	0,001	0,001	0,002
Drinking water	5362	99,6	0,012	0,015	0,017
Herbs, spices and condiments	25	72,0	0,006	0,007	0,007
Food for infants and small children	26	7,7	0,006	0,006	0,006
Composite foods*	-	-	0,004	0,012	0,019
Snacks, desserts, and other foods*	-	-	0,000	0,010	0,020

¹ Occurrence data for the food categories indicated with an asterisk were taken from the relevant EFSA report.

Results – Discussion

The IMPRORISK model results are shown on Table 2 in µg kg⁻¹ body weight per week. The results represent the mean and the 95th percentile exposure at LB, MB and UB scenario. The results are comparable to the results from the EFSA Scientific Report on cadmium⁽²⁾. The mean exposure is at 81% of the TWI and the 95th percentile exposure is at 175% of the TWI, according to the MB scenario.

Table 2: Risk assessment of cadmium in adolescents in Cyprus.

	Dietary exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg b.w./week}$)					
	Mean			95th percentile		
	LB	MB	UB	LB	MB	UB
IMPRORISK model	1.79	2.03	2.66	4.15	4.38	5.42
EFSA ¹	1.70	1.97	2.24	3.70	4.03	4.37
% of TWI ² (IMPRORISK)	71	81	106	166	175	217

¹ Results from the Scientific Report of EFSA, Cadmium dietary exposure in the European population, 2012.

² TWI= 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg b.w.}$ per week

Figures 1 and 2 present the distribution of exposure of the Cypriot adolescent population according to the MB and UB scenario, respectively. It is derived that 24% and 37% of the population exceeds the TWI based on the MB and UB scenario, respectively.

Figure 1: Distribution of Cd exposure for the Cypriot population, based on MB scenario.

Figure 2: Distribution of Cd exposure for the Cypriot population, based on UB scenario

Grain products, fish & other seafood and composite food contribute to more than 50% to the Cd intake based on MBscenario. The food classification is based on level 1 of FoodEx. The contribution of each food category is shown in the Figure 3, and is in accordance with the findings in the relevant EFSA report⁽²⁾.

Figure 3: Contribution of each food category to the total exposure to Cd in Cyprus

Conclusion

The IMPRORISK model results indicate that adolescent dietary Cd exposure estimates are comparable with the respective EFSA values calculated for the Cypriot population in the relevant report⁽²⁾. High consumer exposure exceeds the TWI.

The IMPRORISK model can be used in risk assessment studies. The significance of the IMPRORISK model is increased as, being a simple and not expensive model, it can fill a gap in the field of exposure assessment of contaminants, in addition to the Food Additives Intake Model (FAIM) and Pesticide Residue Intake Model (PRIMo).

References

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